

TABLE S1. Species-specific conserved substitutions in the ITS rDNA region of *Trichophyton benhamiae* clade species

Compared taxa	Number of substitutions	Position of conserved substitution / indel ¹
<i>T. benhamiae</i> × <i>T. concentricum</i>	2	80 (C→T), 526 (T→C)
<i>T. benhamiae</i> × <i>T. europaeum</i>	6	41 (A→G), 43 (T→C), 54 (A→G), 266 (T→C), 471 (A→G), 475 (T→C); indel 609
<i>T. benhamiae</i> × <i>T. japonicum</i>	7	41 (A→G), 43 (T→C), 54 (A→G), 168 (T→C), 266 (T→C), 471 (A→G), 475 (T→C); indel 609
<i>T. benhamiae</i> × <i>T. persicum</i>	12	41 (A→G), 168 (T→C), 230 (G→A), 266 (T→C), 437 (C→T), 456 (A→G), 471 (A→G), 475 (T→C), 476 (C→T), 550 (G→A), 562 (C→T), 564 (C→T); indel 213
<i>T. benhamiae</i> × <i>T. spiraliforme</i>	10	41 (A→G), 168 (T→C), 230 (G→A), 266 (T→C), 471 (A→G), 475 (T→C), 476 (C→T), 550 (G→A), 562 (C→T), 564 (C→T); indel 213
<i>T. concentricum</i> × <i>T. persicum</i>	14	41 (A→G), 80 (T→C), 168 (T→C), 230 (G→A), 266 (T→C), 437 (C→T), 456 (A→G), 471 (A→G), 475 (T→C), 476 (C→T), 526 (C→T), 550 (G→A), 562 (C→T), 564 (C→T); indel 213
<i>T. concentricum</i> × <i>T. europaeum</i>	8	41 (A→G), 43 (T→C), 54 (A→G), 80 (T→C), 266 (T→C), 471 (A→G), 475 (T→C) & 526 (T→C); indel 609
<i>T. concentricum</i> × <i>T. japonicum</i>	9	41 (A→G), 43 (T→C), 54 (A→G), 80 (T→C), 168 (T→C), 266 (T→C), 471 (A→G), 475 (T→C) & 526 (C→T); indel 609
<i>T. concentricum</i> × <i>T. spiraliforme</i>	12	41 (A→G), 80 (T→C), 168 (T→C), 230 (G→A), 266 (T→C), 471 (A→G), 475 (T→C), 476 (C→T), 526 (C→T), 550 (G→A), 562 (C→T), 564 (C→T); indel 213
<i>T. europaeum</i> × <i>T. persicum</i>	10	43 (C→T), 54 (G→A), 168 (T→C), 230 (G→A), 437 (C→T), 456 (A→G), 476 (C→T), 550 (G→A), 562 (C→T), 564 (C→T); indel 213, indel 609
<i>T. europaeum</i> × <i>T. spiraliforme</i>	8	43 (C→T), 54 (G→A), 168 (T→C), 230 (G→A), 476 (C→T), 550 (G→A), 562 (C→T), 564 (C→T); indel 213, indel 609
<i>T. japonicum</i> × <i>T. persicum</i>	9	43 (C→T), 54 (G→A), 230 (G→A), 437 (C→T), 456 (A→G), 476 (C→T), 550 (G→A), 562 (C→T), 564 (C→T); indel 213, indel 609
<i>T. japonicum</i> × <i>T. europaeum</i>	1	168 (C→T)
<i>T. japonicum</i> × <i>T. spiraliforme</i>	7	43 (C→T), 54 (G→A), 230 (G→A), 476 (C→T), 550 (G→A), 562 (C→T), 564 (C→T); indel 213, indel 609
<i>T. persicum</i> × <i>T. spiraliforme</i>	2	437 (T→C), 456 (G→A)

¹ positions based on the ITS alignment deposited in the Dryad digital repository